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Information Hiding Using Audio Steganography - A Survey

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ABSTRACT

Today's large demand of internet applications requires data to be transmitted in a secure manner. Data transmission in public communication system is not secure because of interception and improper manipulation by eavesdropper. So the attractive solution for this problem is Steganography, which is the art and science of writing hidden messages in such a way that no one, apart from the sender and intend recipient, suspects the existence of the message, a form of security through obscurity. Audio steganography is the scheme of hiding the existence of secret information by concealing it into another medium such as audio file. In this paper we mainly discuss different types of audio steganographic methods, advantages and disadvantages.

KEYWORDS

Steganography, Cryptography, Audio Steganography, LSB

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Augmented Reality Platforms for Virtual Fitting Rooms

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ABSTRACT

Multi-sensor body scanners combined with new algorithms and social media technologies have started a revolutionary shift away from the classic desktop paradigm and into the direction of intuitive, “natural interaction” where people interface with the technological world through hand gestures, speech and body language. This article reviews recent examples of Virtual Fitting Rooms (VFRs) and supporting technologies which facilitate the shopping experience by letting customers to try-on apparel and/or mix-and-match accessories without being physically present in the retail shop. These platforms are not only powerful decision tools for the on-line shopper, but also contribute to the fun factor of in-store shopping. Using depth scanning techniques, VFRs can create accurate 3D models of shoppers and meaningfully query retail digital catalogs, filter out non-fitting items and allow customers assess the styling and matching aspects in real time. In addition, omnipresent social networking features allow sending photos or videos of the shopper wearing the apparel for quick feedback. The quality of service provided by current VFRs is sufficiently high to boost sales but also minimize returns due to improper fit.

KEYWORDS

Augmented Reality, 3D scanning, cloth models, simulations

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REVIEW OF FACE DETECTION SYSTEMS BASED ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS ALGORITHMS

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ABSTRACT

Face detection is one of the most relevant applications of image processing and biometric systems. Artificial neural networks (ANN) have been used in the field of image processing and pattern recognition. There is lack of literature surveys which give overview about the studies and researches related to the using of ANN in face detection. Therefore, this research includes a general review of face detection studies and systems which based on different ANN approaches and algorithms. The strengths and limitations of these literature studies and systems were included also.

KEYWORDS

Face Detection, Face Recognition, Artificial Neural Networks

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Content Based Image Retrieval Using Exact Legendre Moments and Support Vector Machine

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ABSTRACT

Content Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) systems based on shape using invariant image moments, viz., Moment Invariants (MI) and Zernike Moments (ZM) are available in the literature. MI and ZM are good at representing the shape features of an image. However, non-orthogonality of MI and poor reconstruction of ZM restrict their application in CBIR. Therefore, an efficient and orthogonal moment based CBIR system is needed. Legendre Moments (LM) are orthogonal, computationally faster, and can represent image shape features compactly. CBIR system using Exact Legendre Moments (ELM) for gray scale images is proposed in this work. Superiority of the proposed CBIR system is observed over other moment based methods, viz., MI and ZM in terms of retrieval efficiency and retrieval time. Further, the classification efficiency is improved by employing Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier. Improved retrieval results are obtained over existing CBIR algorithm based on Stacked Euler Vector (SERVE) combined with Modified Moment Invariants (MMI).

KEY WORDS

CBIR, LM, ELM, Feature Extraction, Support Vector Machine

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Infographics in Education : Review on Infographics Design

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ABSTRACT

One way of handling significant amounts of information is through visual. The infographics can transfer knowledge about a topic faster and more effectively than pure text; however, this condition is depending on the quality and presentation of the infographics. This paper is intended to investigate infographics in various areas and then focusing on its application in education. Besides, designing aspect of infographics was explored since it is important for designing good quality of infographics application. To achieve this objective, a total of 55 articles from four databases covering the period from 2004 to 2016 were analyzed based on their setting. The analysis showed that 30 articles discussed the infographics, eighteen articles elaborated infographics in education field, and seven articles immersed on infographics design. Infographics design techniques in various areas can be implemented in designing a good infographics application for teaching and learning purposes.

KEYWORDS

Infographics, Infographics in Education, Infographics Design

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Color Texture Classification Approach Based on Combination of Primitive Pattern Units and Statistical Features

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ABSTRACT

Texture classification became one of the problems which has been paid much attention on by image processing scientists since late 80s. Consequently, since now many different methods have been proposed to solve this problem. In most of these methods the researchers attempted to describe and discriminate textures based on linear and non-linear patterns. The linear and non-linear patterns on any window are based on formation of Grain Components in a particular order. Grain component is a primitive unit of morphology that most meaningful information often appears in the form of occurrence of that. The approach which is proposed in this paper could analyze the texture based on its grain components and then by making grain components histogram and extracting statistical features from that would classify the textures. Finally, to increase the accuracy of classification, proposed approach is expanded to color images to utilize the ability of approach in analyzing each RGB channels, individually. Although, this approach is a general one and it could be used in different applications, the method has been tested on the stone texture and the results can prove the quality of approach.

KEYWORDS

Texture classification, Grain Components, statistical feature, primitive pattern unit Iris recognition, unconstrained environments, near infrared light, visible wavelength.

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Medical Image Segmentation by Marker Controlled Watershed and Mathematical Morphology

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ABSTRACT

Segmentation by watershed transform is a fast, robust and widely used in image processing and analysis, but it suffers from over-segmentation. We present in this paper some improvements to this algorithm based on the mathematical morphology in order to get over this difficulty. The performance of this method is validated on medical images. The results obtained show the good performance of this approach

KEYWORDS

Image processing, medical image segmentation, watershed, Marker controlled watershed, reconstruction, dilatation, Mathematical morphology.

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An Adaptive Watermarking Technique for the copyright of digital images and Digital Image Protection

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ABSTRACT

The Internet as a whole does not use secure links, thus information in transit may be vulnerable to interruption as well. The important of reducing a chance of the information being detected during the transmission is being an issue in the real world now days. The Digital watermarking method provides for the quick and inexpensive distribution of digital information over the Internet. This method provides new ways of ensuring the sufficient protection of copyright holders in the intellectual property dispersion process. The property of digital watermarking images allows insertion of additional data in the image without altering the value of the image. This message is hidden in unused visual space in the image and stays below the human visible threshold for the image. Both seek to embed information inside a cover message with little or no degradation of the cover-object. In this paper investigate the following relevant concepts and terminology, history of watermarks and the properties of a watermarking system as well as a type of watermarking and applications. We are proposing edge detection using Gabor Filters. In this paper we are proposed least significant bit (LSB) substitution method to encrypt the message in the watermark image file. The benefits of the LSB are its simplicity to embed the bits of the message directly into the LSB plane of cover-image and many techniques using these methods. The LSB does not result in a human perceptible difference because the amplitude of the change is little therefore the human eye the resulting stego image will look identical to the cover image and this allows high perceptual transparency of the LSB. The spatial domain technique LSB substitution it would be able to use a pseudo-random number generator to determine the pixels to be used for embedding based on a given key. We are using DCT transform watermark algorithms based on robustness. The watermarking robustness have been calculated by the Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Normalized cross correlation (NC) is used to quantify by the similarity between the real watermark and after extracting watermark.

KEYWORDS

Watermarking, Steganography, Peak Signal to Noise (PSNR), data hiding, Copyright Protection, Normalized Cross Correlation (NC).

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GAMIFICATION ELEMENTS AND THEIR IMPACTS ON TEACHING AND LEARNING – A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the results of a literature review to identify the elements of gamification in learning that have been applied in previous studies and their impacts on student learning, with only taking into account the related studies within the last three years (2016 to 2018). This is done to determine the most effective and suitable elements of gamification to be applied in our study and at the same time to identify research gaps that need to be fulfilled in future researches. The results of this review show that gamification has positive impact on student learning particularly in their engagement and achievement. Furthermore points, leaderboard and digital badge are the most applied gamification elements in the studies. The findings will be used as a guide for us in designing a gamified collaborative learning activities in the 3-dimensional virtual world that will be carried out later.

KEYWORDS

Gamification, Game-based Learning, Virtual World

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SELECTION SORTING ALGORITHM VISUALIZATION USING FLASH

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ABSTRACT

This paper is intended to develop an algorithm visualization, particularly selection sorting for an Algorithm and Programming course. Algorithm visualization technology graphically illustrates how algorithms work. This visualization can be used to explain how all data move to the proper position in order to be sorted in a display computer for education. This research consists of 6 steps which are concept, design, obtaining content material, assembly, testing, and distribution. During the testing step, the application is run and checked to confirm that it performs exactly what the author has intended and the students can learn selection sorting algorithm by studying the visualization. Subjects of the research were students at Department of Informatics Universitas Persada Indonesia YAI for implementation of the learning. The data were analysed using the analytic descriptive method and interpreted in a narrative way based on the research findings. The algorithm visualization indicates that students increase their motivation and ability to program variety of sorting in programming language they learn.

KEYWORDS

Multimedia, Algorithm, Sorting, Flash movie, ActionScript

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